

A RDM-checklist for supervisors - research data management during Master's thesis

Along with the overall guidance of the undergraduate students with their master's thesis, the supervisor should pay attention to the basics of research data management (RDM). With the help of this checklist, the supervisor can: check that the student takes care of the data management, introduce / pay attention to basic themes and terminology of data management that need to be introduced to the students.

RDM refers to the technical and administrative processing of data. RDM is an integral part of any research and an important general skill, not only in the work of a researcher, but also in other professions, such as professional work in national agencies or in health care. This is why it is important to guide RDM also to the students that are making their Master's thesis.

Research data management begins with good planning. Data management plan (DMP) is a document that describes everything that happens to data during and after a research project (e.g. ownership or access rights, file format, storage locations, sharing with others and related agreements, taking data protection and data security into account). In this checklist, the questions concern these very issues and the checklist guides you and the student to take into account the important RDM issues depending on the data type (e.g. data containing personal data vs. data not containing personal data).

More general information in RDM in [UEF Datasupport website](#) and in UEF's learning material [Research Data Management for Undergraduate Students](#).

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Data Management Plan (DMP)

1. Is there already a DMP document made for the research data of the Master's thesis project?
 Yes
 No

If YES: Please, go through the DMP and check that it address the points on this checklist.

If NO: Please, go through the checklist with the student. Write down the answers and the checklist will also serve as a DMP document.

The source and the rights of use of the data

2. Does the student collect or generate the data themselves for the Master's thesis?
Note: The question is related to the rights of use of the research data. The owner of the rights of use of the research data is able to decide on many issues related to the processing of the research data. If the master's student
- collects the data themselves, as a rule they own the rights of use
- re-uses data collected in UEF, UEF/the research group as the owner owns the rights of use
- conducts a sponsored research for a company, often the owner of the data is the company regardless whether the student collects the data or uses already existing data
 Yes (please, go to the question 4)
 No

3. If the owner of the rights of use of the research data is someone other than the student, is there an agreement between the owner and student on the rights of use of the data that covers: rights of use, access during the research, confidentiality and/or data protection, data processing (e.g. secure storage, disposal)?

- Yes
 No

If YES: Great, the contracts and agreements are in order.

If NO: Take a look at the [UEF Intra for the detailed instructions](#) on how to make contracts and agreements. If needed, contact datasupport@uef.fi.

The processing of the research data that contain personal data and/or clinical data

4. Do the data contain personal data?

- Note that [personal data are any information that can be used to identify a person](#) (name, address, e-mail address, IP address, voice, image, fingerprint, car registration number, rare professional title, small locality, etc...)

- If personal data is collected for the thesis, it is recommended to read [the Data Protection Guide for Students in UEF KAMU](#).

- If the data contain personal data, the processing must follow the regulations of the [GDPR, i.e. the General Data Protection Regulation](#).

- Yes
 No (please, go to the question 11)

5. Has a privacy notice been made for research data containing personal data in accordance with [UEF guidelines](#)?

- Yes
 No

6. In the case of personal data, have the study participants been informed what personal data will be collected in the project and how will the data be processed (e.g. storage, transfer, sharing)?

- Yes
 No

7. Has the data security been taken into account when choosing the storage places and sharing tools for the personal data?

- Yes
 No

8. Are the personal data sensitive (i.e. special categories of personal data) and/or is the project a clinical research project?

- Note that the processing of personal data belonging to so-called special categories of personal data is highly regulated by GDPR. Such information indicates a person's racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, health information, sexual orientation or behaviour, and genetic and biometric data for the purpose of identifying the person.

- Yes
 No

9. Has a prior ethical assessment been done if dealing with sensitive personal data or clinical research?

- Yes
 No

If NO: Help the student to make an ethical pre-assessment. For more information: Clinical Research: [Regional Medical Research Ethics Committee of Wellbeing Services County of North Savo](#) and Research ethics (<https://www.uef.fi/en/research-ethics>)

10. Have [the security in storage places and sharing the data](#) been taken into account if dealing with sensitive personal data?

- Yes
 No

If YES: Check whether the points in question 14 have been taken into account in the DMP.
If NO: The points in question 14 should be taken into account when storing data.

Other confidential information (other than personal data)

11. Do the data contain confidential information, such as trade secret, patent, endangered species, biosecurity, information related to national defence?

- Yes
 No (please, go to the question 14)

12. Have [the security in storage places and sharing the confidential data](#) been taken into account?

- Yes
 No

If YES: Check whether the following points (question 14) have been taken into account in the DMP.

If NO: The points in question 14 should be taken into account when storing data.

13. In the case of confidential data, is there a written agreement between the student and the sponsor (recommended) (see questions 2 and 3)?

- Yes
- No
- Not necessary: Why not? _____

Data storage, information security, backup and transfer

14. Have the following issues been taken into account in the data storage plan? **Tick, if yes.** If not, the student should plan the storage carefully before starting the thesis.

- Where will the data be stored during the thesis process? _____
- Is data security taken into account?
- Is backup planned or is it done automatically? How? _____

Please see [UEF instructions for secure storage solutions and the backup.](#)

15. Is there a need to share the data with others or transfer data from one storage location to another?

- Yes
- No

If YES: Check the [UEF's secure sharing solutions.](#)

Naming, documenting and describing the data

16. Is the storage structure of the data planned (including folders, file formats, file naming, naming different versions of the documents)?

- Yes
- No

If NO, it is worth planning the storage together with the student by giving them some examples of good practices. Please see [UEF's learning material Research Data Management for Undergraduate Students](#) and [Data management Guidelines of Finnish Social Science Data Archive \(FSD\)](#).

17. Are the descriptive information (= metadata of the data) and documentation of the data designed to make the data understandable to both the student and others (e.g. taking notes of data origin, collection procedures, date, variables, etc.)?

Note: Necessary descriptive metadata can be very specific to the discipline or type of data.

- Yes
- No

If NO: Check [the instructions on how to describe your data on the UEF Data Support website.](#)

Preservation, destruction or publication of data after graduation

18. Will the data be preserved after the thesis?

- Yes
- No (please, go to the question 20)

19. When it comes to preserving the data after the graduation, are these things considered?

Tick if yes. If NO: It is a good idea to plan the steps before starting the thesis.

Is the retention period of the data known? For how long the data is preserved?

Is the storage location known? Where are the data stored after the graduation?

Is the file format of the preserved data such that it can be opened by commonly used computer programs now and in the future? What is/are the file format(s)?

Please see the [UEF's guideline for data preserving after the research project](#).

20. Is the destruction of data planned?

- Yes
- No

If NO: Familiarize yourself with [the instructions of proper data destruction on the UEF Data Support website](#).

21. Is the data scientifically valuable enough to be opened or published for re-use?

- Yes
- No

If YES: Contact the UEF Data Support (datasupport@uef.fi)

Finally:

You can save or print this checklist for the student, and complete it with the information needed for carrying out data management in practice. Thus, this will also serve as a data management plan if needed. Update the document together with the student as the data management practices are confirmed along the thesis process.

If you need advice on data management for the thesis, UEF Data Support is happy to help at

datasupport@uef.fi